

A Study of Vocational Guidance in the Context of Vocationalisation of Education

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Samaresh Nath

Associate Professor
Education
Fakiragram College
Kokrajhar,(Assam), India

Abstract

The General Conference of International Labour Organization in its vocational guidance recommendations described, "Vocational Guidance" as "assistance given to an individual in solving problems related to occupational choice and progress with due regard for the individual's characteristics and their relation to occupational opportunity. In the definition adopted by the National Vocational Guidance Association, USA, in 1937, "Vocational Guidance is the process of assisting the individual to choose an occupation, prepare for it, enter upon and progress in it." The vocational guidance is assistance to a person regarding some vocation. Various academic scholars and psychologists have sought the help of various definitions to make clear meaning of vocational guidance. This study investigates the intricacies of vocational guidance within the framework of vocationalization of education. In recent years, there has been a significant paradigm shift towards integrating vocational training into mainstream education systems worldwide. This shift has necessitated a reevaluation of vocational guidance practices to ensure their alignment with the evolving educational landscape. The abstract aims to outline the key objectives, methodologies, and findings of the study. The primary objective of this research is to critically examine the role of vocational guidance in facilitating effective career decision-making among students in the context of vocationalized education. Through a comprehensive literature review the integration of vocational guidance into education presents numerous benefits, including enhanced career readiness and reduced skills gap, there are also challenges such as resource constraints and lack of awareness among stakeholders. Moreover, the study highlights the importance of adopting a holistic approach to vocational guidance, encompassing career exploration, skill development, and personalized support. This study contributes to the ongoing discourse on vocationalization of education by shedding light on the pivotal role of vocational guidance in shaping the career trajectories of students. The findings underscore the need for collaborative efforts between educational institutions, policymakers, and industry stakeholders to ensure the effective implementation of vocational guidance programs within vocationalized educational frameworks.

Keywords Vocational Education, Guidance, Occupational, Academic, Training and Skills.

Introduction

Vocational guidance was defined by 1954 committee of the international labour organizations concerning vocational guidance, as assistance rendered by an individual to another in the latter's solving of problem related to his progress and vocational selection keeping in mind the individual peculiarities or special abilities and their relations with his occupational opportunity. In this manner, the objective of vocational guidance is the proper and complete utilization of a nation's man-power through helping the individual to achieve his development and satisfaction in his profession. An individual should choose a profession that suits his abilities in the order that both he and the nation may profit. It is not possible for any individual to be capable of doing every job. Special kinds of job require particular kinds of skill and special know-how.

The views of the U.S. Commission on National Aid to Vocational Education expressed as far back as 1914, hold good for our country even today after more than even decades. The report says, "there is a great and crying need of providing vocational education to

conserve and develop the resources of the nation, to promote a more productive and a prosperous agriculture, to prevent the waste of home labour, to supplement apprenticeship: to increase the wage earning power of our productive workers, to meet the increasing demand for trained workmen, and to offset the increased cost of living. Vocational education is, therefore, needed as a wise business investment for our nation, because our national prosperity and happiness are at stake and our position in the markets of the world cannot otherwise be maintained.

UNESCO in its recommendation of 1974 on Technical and Vocational Education defined it as a "Comprehensive term embracing those aspects of educational process involving in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life. Such an education would be an integral part of general education and a means of preparing for an occupational field and an aspect of continuing education. Technical and vocational education should further contribute to the achievement of society's goals of greater democratization and social, cultural and economic development, while at the same time developing the potential of the individuals for active participation in the establishment and implementation of these goals.

Objective of study

1. To fulfill the national goals of rural development and the removal of unemployment and distribution.
2. To meet out the needs of poor students by providing them vocational information's.
3. To impart education relevant to productivity, national development, and individual prosperity.
4. To introduce the pupils with the fact that what type of persons is required for some particular vocations and what type of vocation suits a particular type of personality.

Review of Literature

The topic of vocational education and vocational guidance is a very important part of opportunity of economic and individual literature. The available literature can be divided into two parts. One of the groups is in favour of vocational courses. Their argument is based on the general view that vocational and technical courses are necessary in order to acquire the skills required for the economic development of the country. Vocational courses are seen as an alternative option to the general secondary schooling especially for the students with weak academic ability.

Singh (2017) studied on vocational guidance needs of senior secondary school students with regards to their circle of relative type and socio-economic fame. In the prevailing investigation, a pattern of 322 school students reading in magnificence 10+2 from district Kangra of Himachal Pradesh turned into decided on. In the prevailing look at Vocational Guidance Needs Scale evolved through Dr. Meena Buddhisagar Rathod and Mrs. Pallavi Shukla. Socioeconomic Status Scale (SESS) developed by means of R. L. Bhardwaj become used. Results found out that senior secondary school students having high, mild and occasional socio-economic fame did now not fluctuate notably from each other with respect to their vocational guidance needs and possess more or less the same vocational guidance need. Senior secondary school students belonging to nuclear and joint kind of families do now not range notably from every other with respect to their vocational guidance needs. Socio-economic status degree and family kind did not engage drastically in regards to their mixed affect on vocational guidance needs of senior secondary school student. Thuro (1992) referred to developing skills as only sustainable resource. It is also seen as a tool for social inclusion as vocational education is aimed at employment improving lives of unemployed youth and the unprivileged section of the society (Ziderman et al., 1999). Eichhorst et al (2015) regarded vocational education as "silver bullet" for the problem of joblessness amongst youth. They argue that vocational education not only provides the skilled manpower, open door of opportunities for the youth who lack in skills, improve the situation of unemployment and fix the issue of lack of middle level technicians (Neuman and Ziderman, 1999; Oketch, 2007; Eichhorst et al., 2015.)

Psacharopoulos, G. (1997) discussed that vocational education is argued to be as tool to infuse technological knowledge, an alternative for academically weaker students, promote employment, alleviate poverty and encourage globalisation. However, in reality the ground results are far different. The vocational education and training have failed to attract students in the first place. There are reports which confirm that expected benefits from vocational education most often fail to materialize in reality. For example, one reason to advocate vocational education at the secondary level is its usefulness as a tool to generate labour with the medium skills as required by the labour market. The study in countries like Columbia and Tanzania shows that the students who opted for the

vocational training at the school level generally prefer to enter university rather than opting for 14 manual occupations (Psacharopoulos & Loxley, 1985). The study found that academic secondary education is more efficient and effective. Another reason to discourage vocational education and training is the failure to predict the change in skill requirement in the future (Ahmad & Blaug, 1973; Youdi & Himchcliffe, 1985).

Arum & Shavit (1995) used longitudinal data of High School and Beyond of USA to evaluate the effect of vocational education on the employability. The data included information on occupational outcomes of the students from sophomore year in 1980 through 1986. Using the multinomial logit model, the study reached the conclusion that vocational education is not as harmful as described by opponents of vocational education. The study found that vocational education might cause some inhibition amongst students to opt for higher education; however, it also acts as a buffer for the students who did not intend to join higher education at all. Vocational education has been instrumental in providing employment especially to women. McCartney and Teague (2001) pointed that general education is far more flexible as it allows to switch jobs easily as compared to vocational education which is focussed towards specific skill-set. Hanushek et al. (2011) compared labour market outcomes of 18 countries of Europe and United States. The study concluded that vocational education helps in early opportunities for earning livelihood as compared to general education. However, with the age, the general education is more helpful. Oviawe (1970) argued that government might find it difficult to singlehandedly achieve the task of providing technical vocational education and training and therefore public-private partnership shall be encouraged in this direction. Billett (2006) reviewed the literature and pointed out that intent of private enterprise for providing training does not matches with the national goal of skilling the labour force to make them adaptable. Therefore, encouraging enterprises to source training only helps in achieving short-term goal only.

The World Bank Study (1995a, p.8) confidently states that the rate of returns for investment in general education is higher as compared to vocational education at the secondary level. It clearly emphasized that vocational and technical education should be privately funded and is best when imparted in the workplace. The training which is led by the enterprise is generally the most cost-effective way to develop skills in workers. (World Bank, 1995 b). Public funded vocational training is proved to be inefficient and expensive in most of the countries.

Lassibille (2005) calculated returns to education for the country of Rwanda. The data on earnings was taken from the Rwanda Household Living Condition survey for the year 1991-2001. The data is collected by Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning. The study was based on Mincer method. However, to correct the selection bias if any, the study considered two-step model developed by Trost and Lee which is based on Heckman Method. The results highlighted that with the age people prefer to work in public or formal private sector over the informal sector. Individual's choice of sector of employment is influenced by level of education. Ones with the no schooling tend to work in informal sector. Workers with higher education are relatively more likely to work in public formal sector. The study also found out that even though returns from vocational education are positive but are lesser than that of general education.

Kahyarara & Teal (2008) analysed the reason for the strong preference for academic education in Africa even though the level of development is very low and job opportunities are not growing with much speed. They used the data from Tanzania's manufacturing Enterprise survey for the year 2000 and 2002. Using the Mincerian method, the study concluded that higher academic education earns higher returns as compared to the upper level of vocational courses. Also, vocational streams comparatively fetch more returns to those who exited from the academic stream at the lower level. The study failed to reach any conclusion regarding which educational investment should be preferred as the study abstracted from the topic of the cost of supplying different courses. The study clearly maintains that results are influenced by the size of the firm

Neuman & Ziderman (1999) researched on vocational education in Israel. They used the 1983 census data of Israel concerning those workers who did not proceed for higher education after attending secondary school and have work experience of at least three years. Mincerian equation was used to estimate earning function and then regressions were run using the specification suggested by Hotchkiss. The study found that there was a little difference in the earning between the vocational and the general stream. Bennell (1996) in his studies also pointed that social rate of returns for general secondary education is not significantly higher than school-based vocational education.

Duraisamy (2002) used large-scale employment - unemployment data of National sample survey organisation for the year 1983 and 1993-94 to calculate returns to both academic

as well as vocational education in India. Returns to the different level were calculated by using an elaborate method and earning function method. It studied returns by gender, location, and age-cohort. The study demonstrates that technical diplomas/certificates fetch higher returns than that from the college education. The returns are higher for the young population of age cohort 15-29 years. The returns to vocational education and training are higher for rural areas as compared to urban India. The returns to technical education have increased for males. The study did not take into account the family background.

Ryan (2002) analysed the data of Survey of Education and Training, 1997 collected by Australian Bureau of Statistics. The study used the internal rate of return of method to calculate individual returns to vocational education and training qualification. The study concluded that the wages earned by those with vocational education and training varied from the level of vocational qualification achieved. The base level vocational courses gave 10 percent lesser returns as compared to the diploma courses.

Bishop & Mane (2003) reviewed the literature on the analysis of secondary vocational education. Graphical analysis is supplemented by a statistical tool like regression. They found evidence of growing returns on the technical courses. The skill requirements of business have increased and witnessed a rapid shift during the 1980s and the 1990s which made vocational education more effective. The study analyzed longitudinal data on students of high school in the U.S. The occupation-specific training has a positive effect on income. In order to overcome the selection bias, they increased the sample size and variables. This may give rise to endogeneity bias and hence, was not the best choice for dealing with such type of research question.

McIntosh (2004) conducted a study on labour force survey of the United Kingdom. The main focus was to see the impact of vocational qualification on employability skills of individuals who left school in mid. The descriptive analysis technique is used. The study showed that vocational qualification helps in improving the employability of those who are dropouts from schools. However, the route of vocational qualification is followed by a few school leavers.

Parhar, Kaur and Kaur (2018) studied the guidance needs of secondary students of Jalandhar District. Normative Survey approach become used. Random sampling approach was used to gather the facts. A sample of two hundred rural and urban, male and female, students become taken through random sampling approach. The findings of the examine indicated that there has been no significant distinction between the guidance desires (educational, social, physical, mental, and vocational) of female and male secondary school students and the guidance needs of rural secondary college students had been more than those of urban secondary school students.

Walia (2017) studied the connection between Vocational Guidance Needs and Family atmosphere of adolescents analyzing in Government Senior Secondary Schools, situated in rural areas of district Ludhiana. The sample of 480 adolescents reading in Government Senior Secondary Schools situated in rural regions of Ludhiana district become selected. The standardized tools, for every variable, were used to collect the statistics from decided on sample. Analysis of collected records become carried out the use of special descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. Results discovered extensive dating between variables of Vocational guidance needs and Self-concept of adolescents.

Cheryl and Eric (2016) studied the services supplied with the aid of rural and urban secondary school counselors across Pennsylvania. Specifically, this studies examined historic records on in line with scholar spending on steering offerings throughout the commonwealth and used survey facts of secondary expert school counselors to perceive the provision of resources, the needs of school students and interventions used to satisfy the ones wishes, counseling curriculum development, and guidance on STEM associated schooling and careers. There are 500 public school districts in the common wealth, 497 of which were used in the evaluation of secondary facts. Of those 497 districts, 234 are rural and 263 districts are city. The statistics indicate city faculty counselors are spending greater time on individual career and post-secondary counseling than are rural faculty counselors. It became found that rural students want extra vocational guidance than urban students.

Crisan, Pavelea and Ghimbulut (2015) conducted a study on desires assessment on school students career guidance and career counseling packages within the university. The research is based totally on a survey advanced on a sample of a hundred thirty college students from the College of Political, Administrative and Communication Science, Babes-Bolyai University ClujNapoca. The gathered statistics has been each qualitative and quantitative. The students were inquired about their professional course, about their career selections, non-public and professional values, talents and talents,

intentions for the future and many others. The most relevant consequences of the look at display that: students are poorly knowledgeable about activity opportunities, their expectancies for the future aren't connected with their personal know-how and talents, they do now not have a coherent career plan and encounter primary barriers within the profession decision system.

Sharma and Kaur (2012) aimed to study the guidance needs of 200 students of 9th grade of Ludhiana District in relation to gender, locale and type of school by using the Guidance needs Inventory by J. S. Grewal. The study revealed no significant difference in guidance needs of adolescent boys and girls 41 while significant difference was found in guidance needs of rural and urban, government and private school adolescents. The students of government and private schools differed significantly for their guidance needs.

Shukla (2011) conducted a study on Vocational Guidance needs in relation to Values, Aptitude & Creativity of higher secondary school student of Indore district. Government school students had been determined to have more vocational guidance needs as compared to private schools. Vocational guidance needs was found to be independent of interaction between gender and religious value, gender and social value, gender and democratic value, gender and aesthetic value, gender and economic value, gender and knowledge value, gender and hedonistic value, gender and power value and gender and health value.

Palos and Drobot (2010) conducted study to identify a few variables from the own family surroundings that have an effect on adolescent selection for a future career. The pattern: 60 students from the final high-school grade. The test portfolio: Parent Career Behavior Checklist (Keller and Whiston, 2008); EMBU questionnaire (Perris et al, 1980); Adult Attachment Scale (Collins and Read, 1990). The acquired results provide us a picture of the variables which have an effect on profession choice making technique and the manner in which vocational counseling and the role of the counselor are perceived in school.

William and Straues, et.al, (2010) conducted a research on social status and educational and vocational aspiration among the more than four thousand Wisconsin high school seniors in all parts of the state to test the hypothesis in respect of level of occupational aspiration of youth and their families where the effects of intelligence were controlled. In the end, it was concluded that among both high schools boys and girls there was significant association between the level of vocational aspiration and the social status of their families

Yaegel (1990) observed that females were found to be significantly more certain about their vocational choice than males in his study on 'certainty of vocational choice'

Mishra (1990) investigated the connection between vocational interests and SES. His examine additionally aimed to discover the impact of gender and residence on vocational interests. The sample consisted of 200 students a hundred urban and a hundred rural. SES became discovered to be positively related with administrative and scientific hobbies and negatively related with agriculture and social provider areas of interest.

Tabassum (2014) studied a relationship of educational stress on achievement motivation and habit of study amongst secondary school students. It have become found that educational pressure of higher secondary students of UP Board become negatively correlated with achievement motivation. It was discovered that academic pressure of UP Board of females and males turned into negatively correlated with achievement motivation. It became discovered that achievement motivation of higher secondary school of UP Board became definitely correlated with habit of study. It was discovered that academic stress, success motivation and habit of study of higher secondary students of UP Board have interactional relation with each other.

Mahapatra (2007) studied that there is no significant effect on the academic stress and teaching success by the regional background of the B.Ed students.

Vyas (2006) Confirmed that age of the pupil – instructors of Teacher Training Institutes (TTIs) have tremendous in their degree of instructional strain The higher the age of the scholar instructors, the stress is lowered.

Anice James and Marice (2004) studied the effect of academic strain at the achievement of the XI students and discovered a significant distinction between male and female. Females found better than boys in their degree of success and lower in the degree of educational stress.

Jagannadhan (2003) studied that there is no significant influence on V, VI and VII class student's level of academic stress and achievement by birth order.

Kumaraswami (2003) indicated that the adult student's age did not affect the academic stress in the arithmetic, writing and reading as well as in whole area. Panda (1998) studied that the students of ninth and tenth class belong to small families have been higher of their stage of academic stress than the scholars dwelling with the big families.

Pukar and Bartolovic (1993) investigated 222 normal students in a rural high school. The students stated experiencing disturbing activities associated to school, friendship, own family, health and transportation. The research is necessary in view of the contribution closer to know-how the stressor confronted by rural youth; but, lack of standardized tools to compute it keeps, the area of the findings restrained.

Ramamalini (1993) studied on academic stress and level of family help and intelligence in a specific organization of high school female students stated 53 no significant relationship between them. But a substantial correlation was discovered among academic stress and own family support.

Dubois, Felner, Brand and Evans (1992) investigated employed a 2-yr longitudinal layout to examine the relation of annoying existence occasions and social helps to psychological misery and school performance amongst 166 early adolescents. Results confirmed that both pressure and support variables made notable contributions to the forecast of following school performance.

Sevenaaks and Kent (1992) suggested that handwriting leaves an everlasting record of hand motion and is generally influenced and disrupted by strain from a selection of resources. Actual physical pressure can be as a result of the act of writing this can be the result of bad postural techniques, exacerbated via the call for of speed and academic stress.

Sears and Milburn (1983) in their book 'Stress in Children and Adolescents' summarized common pressure among the schooling children. As the main developmental mission of this level worries schooling a number of the stresses are school associated. School associated issues, in general are test taking, school fears. For example, homework and worry of failure or success inclusive of school phobia.

Bisht (1980) investigated the impact of school atmosphere and want for academic achievement on the academic pressure of students and found that academic stress did not influenced independently, but their relation become statistically significant among the four components of academic stress annoyance, conflict stress and tension.

Feinberg et al., (2003) – discovered the link between siblings dissimilarity in track of change inside the characteristics of parent child relationship and the features of sibling relationship across a 2-years period in childhood. The result supports the view that sibling differentiation can be an approach for dealing with sibling struggle and competition.

Crooks (2003) designed to explore the importance of father and mother and peer guide in middle adolescent and early, formative years across two time intervals –this study verify the need for a more contextual technique to research inspecting completing and compensatory effect on adolescent improvement.

Overbeek et al., (2002) – Tested cross-sectional and longitudinal relation between overdue adolescent parental attachment and emotional disturbance, specifically, the discovered whether relation between parental attachment and emotion disruption had been less strong for teenagers with romantic partners, 56 and whether the equality and duration of romantic relationship had been associated with teenagers emotional trouble

Jogawar (1982) – created an inventory to compute perceived self, ideal self, and social self among Indian teenage. The inventory was administrated to 880 adolescents (elderly thirteen to 20 yrs) of Amravati and the result imply that whose mother and father accepted them had greater self- regard that whose parents rejected them. Rohner (1976) studied the Parental Acceptance – Rejection Questionnaire (PARQ) in three forms – mother, infant and adults, includes 60 items and measures the level of courting between mother and infant as perceived through them independently. The adolescents form calculate the connection of an adolescent as perceived through him towards his/her mother.

Selvaraj and Gnanadevan (2016) studied on the "Relationship between self-confidence and academic achievement of higher secondary students". The study discovered the relation between self-confidence and educational achievement of higher secondary students. The pattern included 620 males and females studying in higher secondary in Cuddalore District of Tamil Nadu. The study discovered positive relation between self-confidence and academic achievement of higher secondary students.

Meena Sharma (2016) studied the self-confidence of higher secondary school students in relation to socio-economic status. The sample was taken through survey method. Sample comprised of 180 students of higher secondary school from Rohtak district. The researcher used Socio-economic status scale (2006) developed by Singh, Shyam and Kumar and Self-Confidence Inventory (1987) developed by Agnihotry (ASCI). Result of the study was no significant variation in self-confidence of those boys and girls who belong to low Socioeconomic status and high Socio-economic status.

Dabas (2015) studied on "Sport self-confidence as a psychological characteristic among Indian Paralympics sportsmen and ordinary athletes". The purpose of the study became to analyze the sport self-confidence (Trait and State) as a psychological feature among Indian Paralympics sportsmen and normal athletes. For the cause of the study 60 male Paralympics sportsmen and 60 male everyday athletes were decided on randomly all through the respective National Championships. This examine discovered that the Paralympics sportsmen possessed extra trait sport self-confidence in contrast to normal athletes; while significant distinction was discovered between Paralympics 60 sportsmen and ordinary athletes. A better degree of trait sport self-confidence in Paralympics sportsmen may be because of their better self-confidence by way of trait in compare to everyday athletes. Finally, vast distinction was discovered between exceptional games of Paralympics sportsmen in terms of trait recreation self-confidence.

Goel and Jaspreet (2015) studied on "Self-confidence of 10th class students with regards to sex and locale". The objectives were to study the selfconfidence of 10th class students of Sri Muktsar Sahib District, to observe the difference between self-confidence of boys and girls, rural and urban students. The sample comprised of sixty students of tenth class of Sri Muktsar Sahib District. Sample was collected through Stratified random sampling method. The study discovered no vast distinction between self-confidence of boys and girls, rural and urban of tenth class students of Sri Muktsar Sahib District.

Prasad (2015) conducted a study on "Relationship between self-idea and self-confidence". The study was taken to analyze the self-concept and selfconfidence rural and urban students, and to study the sex variations in self-idea and self-confidence. The sample consisted of 140 students (70 rural and 70 urban) from Chhattisgarh. Self-concept become measured with the aid of selfconcept rating scale and self-confidence turned into measured by way of selfconfidence inventory. The findings indicated that there had been no significant differences in regards to the self-concept of male and female and urban and rural students. Significant sex variations had been located in self-confidence rating. The females had significantly better degree of self-confidence in comparison to the males. The basic consequences indicated that self-idea and self-confidence have been positively correlated. It implies that teenagers having high self-idea would have excessive self- confidence. But in self-confidence sex plays an enormous position.

Kumar and Santha (2014) studied "Self-confidence and emotional adjustment of higher secondary students". The study found the connection between self-confidence and emotional adjustment of higher secondary students 61 primarily based on their sex, locale and kind of management. The findings found out a positive relationship between self-confidence and emotional adjustment.

Gupta (2013) conducted a study on construction and standardization of self-confidence scale of instructors. The sample were accumulated from Gujarat. It became discovered that granted and non-granted teachers do no longer vary in their self-confidence. It was discovered that CBSE and GSEB Board teachers do no longer vary of their self-confidence. Open and other class teachers do now not fluctuate in their self-confidence. The adult males and female teachers do no longer vary in their self-confidence.

Deirdre (2012) conducted a study on developing pre-service Primary Teachers Confidence and Competence in Arts Education using Principles of Authentic Learning, Australian Journal of Teacher Education, Volume 37, 1. Few students showed that they felt assured or capable on the subject of arts education. They suggested a selection of procedures which would assist them expand this self-assurance and these have been compared with the deliberate content material of the problem. At the cease of the semester, most of the students agreed that that they had evolved self-assurance and competence in arts educations. They listed key elements of the problem that helped them

gain this confidence and competence and those included the assessment objects and the realistic tutorials and lectures.

Dhall&Thakral (2000) investigated intelligence as associated with selfconfidence and academic success of school students. The outcomes of the look at revealed that intelligence is considerably and positively associated with selfconfidence and academic success.

Deshmukh (2000) studied on anxiety, intelligence, purpose discrepancy achievement motivation, and educational achievement of junior university students with high and low self-concept. The study found that high and low selfconcept groups of junior college students vary considerably on anxiety and intelligence. These groups do not vary considerably on goal disparity and academic success.

Lee (1996) studied the relationship between L2 learner's anxiety, selfconfidence and oral performance. The findings of the analyses confirmed that there had been significant influence of anxiety and self-confidence on L2 learners oral performance. The higher anxious the students have been approximately talking English, the lower scores they received on their performance. The higher confident they had been, the higher oral performance they showed the correlation analyses of anxiety / confidence and the elements of oral performance showed that confidence was more closely correlated with the L2 learner's attitude and interaction along with communication techniques and social communication skills of oral performance, while anxiety became mare negatively correlated with the L2 learner's range of oral performance such as vocabulary and grammar.

Salomone (1982) found that individuals who were not able to make their future career decisions were characterized by low self-confidence.

Methodology

The methodology for vocational guidance using secondary data typically involves:

Data Collection: Gather secondary data from various sources such as research reports, academic journals, and industry publications. At a Analysis: Analyze the secondary data to identify trends, patterns, and opportunities in different vocational fields, including job growth, salary trends, required skills, and educational pathways. Identifying Target Audience Determine the demographic and psychographic characteristics of the target audience for vocational guidance, such as age, interests, skills, and educational background. Developing Guidance Materials: Create guidance materials based on the analyzed secondary data, including career profiles, educational requirements, job outlooks, and skill assessments. Feedback and Evaluation Collect feedback from users to assess the effectiveness of the vocational guidance materials and make necessary improvements based on the evaluation. Continuous Monitoring Continuously monitor secondary data sources for updates and changes in the job market and vocational trends to keep the guidance materials relevant and up-to-date

Result and Discussion

Vocational Education and Vocational Guidance Both are intimately related. One is incomplete without the other. Vocational guidance will not only be incomplete but also a meaningless attempt, if it is not followed by an adequate programmed of vocational education. On the other hand, the programmed of vocational education cannot be effectively implemented if it is not preceded by vocational guidance George E. Mayers has described this relations "Vocational education without vocational guidance is much like trying to make an automobile crankshaft out of sty bar of metal that comes handy without first determining whether it is suitable for the purpose. Vocational guidance without vocational education is like selecting with great care a bar of steel suitable for a crank shaft without providing proper facilities for subjecting it to the process of forming tempering and gauging for the purpose Both vocational guidance and vocations education are necessary to a successful transfer from school to necessary working life."

Vocational Guidance Activities of the School Vocational Guidance activities of the school have a two-fold role to play ineffective implementation of the Scheme of Vocationalisation of Education:

1. Providing necessary guidance to students, parents, and faculty members with regard to educational and vocational choices
2. Helping in actual administration and smooth functioning of the programme.
3. Teaching dignity of labour and basic desirable attitudes towards manual work.

4. Understanding of the world of work and the principles involved in different forms of work. Such information will be disseminated through a number of exploratory and career education activities like class projects, career albums, preparation of charts and posters, visits, field trips and other kinds of exposure to work and skills required in various forms of work.

5. Considering that a lot of flexibility of students according to the provisions of facilities in the school and according to the choices of students based on their likes, dislikes, and capabilities and other factors is required to be done. A lot of exploratory work into the personal assessments and personality characteristics of individuals will be required. Hence the required psychological appraisal of pupils for identification of relevant data will be done by guidance counselors

6. In view of the fact that vocational courses are terminal in nature, such information as job openings, methods of applying and obtaining jobs, scope and opportunities for self employment and wage employment, etc., has to be coordinated with the students' future career plans.

7. The school counselor will also have the important job of helping the 2 passed-outs in finding on the job training and/or placement by working in collaboration with employees and the Employment exchanger Carver guidance activities like reviewing discussing the applicants qualification and interests in relation to available employment opportunities will be required

8. The guidance worker is expected to keep and maintain liaison between pupils, educational sector, and the employment sector at local, district, and state level

The National Review Committee (1978) has recommended that counselling and placement officers be appointed in clusters of three or four schools, particularly in rural areas to start with. Their function will be to advise students with a rural or urban poverty background on the choice of elective subjects, and organize for them remedial courses to make up deficiencies in interested areas. The Committee also recommended that help in placement of students should be provided by having a close liaison with the related agencies.

Occupational Surveys and the Role of the School Counselor:-

The NCERT document, "Higher Secondary Education and Its Vocationalization" suggests a survey of activities to find out employment opportunities, both wage and self. for an area unit or a district. The local employment opportunities could be exploited and imbalance between man power shortages and surpluses in various fields of work could be reduced to minimum. Proper linkages between the District Man-Power and Employment Generation Councils, the Employers in the District, and the schools have to be established to determine the nature and scope of such surveys, the actual information, and the publication of such reports. At the school level, school counsellor is the most appropriate person, who, by virtue of his intensive training and background in collection of occupational information and related skills can help plan the contents and format of the information to be collected in the occupational survey.

Infrastructural Facilities

The conduct of occupational surveys helps in selection and location of appropriate vocational courses and on-the-job training, but the actual administration of the programmes has to be coordinated with the manpower planning and other statutory bodies and the employing agencies within the community. The school guidance counsellor will establish such links, coordinate the programmes and ensure the smooth functioning of the system. He will keep in touch with the statutory bodies like Nursing Council, Pharmacy Council, ICMR, Boards of Technical Education, the ITI's and the Directorate General of Employment and Training. The Programme of Action 1986 has recommended setting up of National Level and State Level Councils for Vocational Education which would be Apex bodies with the membership of all statutory bodies could also be a The school guidance part of these bodies, they would serve part as a bridge between educational administrators and these statutory counsellors life and the community as a whole.

Development of Vocational Skills

Basic objective of the scheme of Vocationalization of Education issue objective of the development of vocational skills in the students, thereby making them more gainfully employable either through self of hereby making meant invocations chosen by them. Between 50% and 80% of the total Instructional time for the study and practice of vocational elective has been recommended by various committees on vocation elective. It is suggested that a reasonable amount of vocationalization time be earmarked for Career Education which is aimed at providing such educational experiences to the students as would "facilitate his career development and preparation for the world of work". It is also proposed that the guidance worker may take these classes on Career Education in collaboration with vocational teachers who may be full-time or part-time representatives from various industries. Vocational education subjects are mainly skill subjects and the teacher of vocational subjects should know the pedagogy and skills in affective training besides vocational training. The teacher and the guidance worker both will have to see that the students have developed vocational skills like quality of job and the systematic and orderly manipulative skills. Such work habits like dignity of labour, diligence and perseverance, cooperative attitude, quick decision, initiative, planning etc., are the affective components of vocational and career education, development of which will be the concern of a guidance counselor in the vocation field.

Conclusion

Vocational guidance is very important for every educational field this time vocational educational and vocationalisation all the institution now modern educational technology, individual educational capacity is need in our society. Vocational education our students properly understand by the guidance of education in the several institutions. These are some important vocational guidance-

Reiteration of the Significance of Vocational Guidance: Vocational guidance serves as a vital tool in empowering individuals to make informed career decisions that align with their interests, abilities, and aspirations.

Reflecting on Personal Growth and Fulfillment: Through vocational guidance, individuals gain clarity about their strengths and preferences, leading to enhanced self-awareness and confidence in pursuing fulfilling career paths.

Addressing Economic and Societal Needs: Effective vocational guidance plays a crucial role in addressing skills mismatches, reducing unemployment, and fostering economic growth by connecting individuals with in-demand careers.

Promoting Equity and Inclusivity:

Access to quality vocational guidance services ensures equitable opportunities for all individuals, irrespective of their background, fostering social inclusion and reducing disparities in employment outcomes.

Navigating the Evolving World of Work: In an era of rapid technological advancements and changing job landscapes, vocational guidance equips individuals with the adaptability and resilience needed to navigate the complexities of the modern workforce.

Collaborative Efforts for Sustainable Impact: Building strong partnerships among educational institutions, government agencies, employers, and community organizations is essential for the effective delivery of vocational guidance services and maximizing their impact.

Continuous Learning and Improvement: Emphasizing the importance of ongoing research, evaluation, and innovation to enhance the quality and relevance of vocational guidance programs and ensure they meet the evolving needs of individuals and industries.

Empowering Individuals for Lifelong Success: Ultimately, vocational guidance empowers individuals to embark on meaningful career journeys, enabling them to achieve their full potential, contribute to society, and lead fulfilling lives.

This conclusion encapsulates the overarching themes of vocational guidance, emphasizing its multifaceted benefits and calling for collaborative efforts to support individuals in navigating their career paths effectively. Feel free to elaborate further on each point and tailor the conclusion to resonate with the specific context and audience of your essay.

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